

AN INTEGRATED AI-DRIVEN DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM FRAMEWORK FOR TEACHING AND LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. Higher education institutions are facing new challenges due to declining enrolment, coping with policy shifts, fragmented data infrastructure, and the growing influence of generative AI. Conventional Decision Support Systems (DSS) that rely on deterministic logic and static datasets are no longer adequate for addressing the complexity of modern higher education environments. While substantial literature discusses the application of AI in specific educational tasks, there remains a lack of a comprehensive framework that integrates predictive intelligence, risk-aware modelling, uncertainty representation, and trust-centric to provide a holistic view on AI infusion within the teaching and learning processes, particularly for supporting strategic decisionmaking. To fill this gap, this paper proposes the Integrated AI-Driven DSS Framework for the Higher Education Ecosystem, a conceptual framework consisting of four interdependent pillars: AI-Driven Predictive Intelligence, RiskAware Modelling, Fuzzy Logic-Based Uncertainty Representation, and Rigorous Usability Validation. The proposed framework is developed based on a critical review of the DSS literature in educational contexts, addressing the gap of existing AI applications are often designed in isolation for specific tasks, which constraint their ability to support decision makers with a comprehensive, integrated, and institution-wide perspective for governing the core functions of higher education ecosystems. The proposed framework contributes to the advancement of proactive, transparent, and accountable decision-making in higher education.

Keywords: decision support system; artificial intelligence; higher education; fuzzy logic; predictive analytics; risk-aware modelling

1. INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions (HEIs) are confronted with increasing operational complexity driven by a combination of internal and external pressures. Declining student enrolment, coping with policy shifts, fragmented institutional data systems, and the unregulated use of generative AI tools have significantly challenged institutional decision-making in higher education [1][2][3][4]. Decision Support Systems (DSS) have been widely used to assist organizational decision-making in various uncertain, complex environments since DSS were introduced in 1970s. In higher education, DSS applications range from strategic governance management, student lifecycle management, academic curriculum management, human resource management to resource allocation and quality assurance reporting [5][6]. However, existing DSS in higher education are predominantly based on deterministic rule logic and static datasets, making them less capable of handling the large volume of complex, heterogeneous, dynamic, and evolving educational data-driven generated from multiple institutional platforms. These

systems are designed for isolated operational functions and structured decision environments, resulting in fragmented systems that operate independently.

The emergence of artificial intelligence, particularly machine learning (ML) and natural language processing (NLP), has provided new opportunities to transform DSS from reactive reporting tools into proactive decision engines [7][8][9]. AI-driven systems are capable of processing high-dimensional, heterogeneous data streams in real time, identifying hidden risk patterns, and generating actionable recommendations under uncertain conditions. This capability represents a significant advancement over traditional DSS, which relies on small, structured datasets and deterministic logic. Despite these developments, a significant gap remains between what AI-driven DSS can offer and what is currently available in higher education ecosystem. A review of the literature indicates the effectiveness of AI-driven DSS within higher education is constrained by unreliability data quality, fragmented institutional data, and the continued reliance on outdated and non-integrated legacy systems, which collectively prevents accurate, holistic, and efficient decision-making [3]. In addition, the integration of AI within DSS framework has significantly enhanced student enrolment strategies through predictive recruitment analytics [10], strengthening student outcomes through learning analytics and dropout prediction models[11][12], and optimizing institutional resource allocation [13]. However, these AI applications in educational decision support are largely task-specific, operating in isolation without integration into broader institutional governance architectures. Furthermore, few existing frameworks formally address the inherent ambiguity in educational decisions, where institutional priorities are often expressed in imprecise or conflicting terms that cannot be adequately handled by crisp numerical models.

This paper addresses these gaps by proposing the Integrated AI-Driven DSS Framework for the Higher Learning Ecosystem. The framework integrates four interdependent pillars: AI-Driven Predictive Intelligence, Risk-Aware Modelling, Fuzzy Logic-Based Uncertainty Representation, and Institutional Trust-Centric. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a review of related work on DSS and AI-driven approaches in higher education. Meanwhile, Section 3 identifies the critical gaps that motivate this research. Section 4 describes the proposed AIDSS-HLE framework and its components. Section 5 discusses the implications and limitations of the framework. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and outlines directions for future research.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 *Decision Support Systems in Higher Education*

DSS have been widely studied and applied in higher education for various administrative and academic functions, particularly in structured decision environments such as timetabling, enrolment management, admission planning, and resource allocation, where decision parameters are relatively stable and welldefined [14][15][16]. These systems were predominantly model-driven or datadriven, relying on inflexible deterministic rules, optimization algorithms and predefined query interfaces to assist administrative decision-making.

Over time, DSS applications in higher education expanded to support more complex governance and evaluation functions. Scholarship selection systems increasingly adopted Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) techniques such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Weighted Sum Model (WSM), and Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) to rank student candidates against multiple institutional criteria in a more structured, transparent, and objective

manner [17]. Similarly, class allocation and teacher appraisal systems have been developed to support academic management using structured performance data and rule-based logic [18]. However, each of these systems operates independently without integration into a broader institutional decision architecture.

The key observation from this body of work is that existing educational DSS are characterized by task-specific isolation. As noted by Mora et. al [19], current implementations demonstrate methodological rigour within bounded contexts, but they rarely scale to address interconnected teaching and learning risks at the institutional level. The lack of interoperability between systems for student management, curriculum compliance, financial planning, and quality assurance means that institutional leaders are often confronted with fragmented and conflicting information.

2.2 Limitations of Traditional DSS

The limitations of traditional DSS in modern higher education can be grouped into three main categories: logical rigidity, data inadequacy, and temporal reactivity.

Logical rigidity in conventional DSS refers to the dependence on deterministic and rule-based reasoning mechanisms that assume stable, explicitly quantifiable inputs, predefined decision rules, and fixed criteria weights, thereby limiting system adaptability in dynamic and uncertain decision environments [20]. In reality, educational decisions frequently involve ambiguity, subjectivity, and shifting institutional priorities. The judgements of administrators, academic staff, and external regulators often conflict, and decision criteria such as programme quality or faculty performance are inherently imprecise. As a result, deterministic models tend to either oversimplify the decision space or fail when faced with contextual changes.

Data inadequacy refers to the inability of traditional systems to process the volume, velocity, variety, and variability of contemporary institutional data. Modern higher education environments generate continuous streams of heterogeneous data from Learning Management Systems (LMS), Student Information Systems (SIS), Academic Information Systems (AIS), IoT sensors, and social media platforms [21][22]. Traditional DSS, designed for small, structured spreadsheets and periodic batch processing, are not architecturally capable of handling these high-dimensional data flows in real time.

Temporal reactivity is widely recognized as a major limitation of conventional Decision Support Systems, as these systems primarily rely on historical and retrospective data processing to generate descriptive reports, thereby limiting the ability of institutions to anticipate emerging risks, respond dynamically to changing conditions, and support proactive strategic governance [23]. By the time a report is generated and acted upon, the institutional conditions it describes may have already changed. This reactive orientation prevents administrators from engaging in proactive, strategic governance and instead traps them in a cycle of crisis management.

2.3 AI-Driven Approaches in Educational Decision Support

The integration of AI into educational DSS has grown considerably in recent years. AI-driven systems offer three key capabilities that traditional DSS lack: predictive modelling, pattern recognition in high-dimensional data, and adaptive learning from new information [24]. Machine learning algorithms, including Random Forests, Gradient Boosting methods, and Deep Neural Networks, have been successfully applied in predicting student dropout risk, academic performance, and learning outcomes in higher education environments [25]. These models are capable of identifying subtle, non-linear relationships among engagement metrics, assessment results, and demographic variables that conventional statistical methods would miss. Meanwhile,

NLP techniques have been applied to the automated analysis of qualitative feedback, sentiment extraction from student evaluations, and the parsing of regulatory policy documents [26][27].

Fuzzy logic has emerged as a particularly useful complement to quantitative AI techniques in educational contexts. By encoding linguistic variables such as "high risk" or "moderate performance" as membership functions rather than crisp numerical values, fuzzy systems can process the inherently imprecise judgements of multiple institutional stakeholders and aggregate them into coherent, analytically defensible outputs. Fuzzy MCDM has been applied to scholarship selection, faculty evaluation, and programme quality assessment, demonstrating its capacity to produce robust prioritisation outcomes even in high uncertainty environments [28][29].

However, as far as we concern, no comprehensive framework has been proposed that integrates predictive analytics, risk modelling, uncertainty representation, and usability validation into a unified decision support architecture specifically designed for higher education governance. Moreover, the critical dimension of institutional trust, the extent to which academic administrators will rely on AI-generated recommendations remains under addressed in existing systems.

2.4 Trust and Explainability in AI-Driven Systems

A recurring finding in the technology adoption and educational technology literature is that the uptake of AI-driven tools in institutional settings depends heavily on user trust, as trust significantly influences perceived usefulness, acceptance intention, readiness, and effective adoption of AI-enabled educational technologies [30]. Complex algorithms, regardless of their predictive accuracy, are likely to be disregarded or resisted if their reasoning is not transparent to the administrators and academics expected to act on their outputs. This concern is particularly relevant in higher education, where decisions carry significant ethical and professional consequences for students and staff.

Explainable AI (XAI) has been developed specifically to address this challenge by making AI decision logic transparent, interpretable, and auditable [31]. In the context of educational DSS, XAI principles translate into the requirement that systems not only generate recommendations but also provide traceable justifications that align with institutional values.

3. IDENTIFIED GAPS

Based on the review of related work, four critical gaps are identified that collectively motivate the development of the integrated AI-driven DSS framework for the higher education ecosystem. These gaps are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE I. Summary of Identified Gaps in Existing Educational DSS

Gap	Description	Implication
Task-Specific Isolation	AI-DSS operate in bounded domains without institutional-level integration	No holistic governance view
Logical Rigidity	Deterministic logic cannot model ambiguity or shifting priorities	Poor fit for educational complexity

Data Architecture Mismatch	Traditional systems cannot process real-time, highdimensional data	Reactive rather than proactive decisions
Trust and Adoption Deficit	Opacity of AI reasoning undermines user trust	Capable systems remain unused

The gap of task-specific isolation reflects the absence of any framework that spans the full breadth of institutional decision domains. The gap of logical rigidity arises because most systems rely on crisp numerical inputs, ignoring the linguistic and qualitative nature of institutional knowledge. The gap of data architecture mismatch reflects the inability of traditional systems to ingest and process heterogeneous real-time data streams. The trust and adoption gap reflects the failure of existing frameworks to treat explainability and usability as core design requirements. Together, these gaps define the design space for the proposed framework.

4. THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

4.1 Framework Overview

The integrated AI-driven DSS framework is proposed as an architectural blueprint for intelligent academic governance. It consists of four interdependent pillars unified under the overarching goal of supporting proactive, transparent, and evidence-based institutional decision-making. Table 2 presents a comparison between traditional DSS and the proposed framework.

TABLE II. Comparison of Traditional DSS and the Proposed Framework

Dimension	Traditional DSS	Proposed Framework
Data Focus	Static, structured datasets	Real-time, highdimensional
Logic Basis	Deterministic rules	Probabilistic, fuzzy, prescriptive
Decision Type	Retrospective reporting	Predictive and prescriptive
Uncertainty Handling	Ignored or simplified	Formally modelled via FMCDM
Scope	Task-specific silos	Unified institutional architecture

4.2 Pillar 1: AI-Driven Predictive Intelligence

The first pillar transforms the DSS from a retrospective reporting tool into a proactive decision engine. ML components perform predictive modelling of student outcomes including dropout risk and academic performance trajectories using data from LMS activity logs, student information, assessment records, and attendance data. Anomaly detection algorithms identify unusual patterns in grade distributions or LMS engagement that may indicate quality or integrity issues. NLP components enable automated ingestion of regulatory policy documents, real-time compliance monitoring against accreditation standards, and sentiment analysis of student and staff feedback. Together, these capabilities support the transition from reactive reporting to forward-looking institutional intelligence [8].

4.3 Pillar 2: Risk-Aware Modelling

The second pillar translates predictive outputs into prioritised, actionable intelligence aligned with institutional governance objectives. Risk in higher education is multidimensional, encompassing academic, financial, operational, and reputational dimensions. This pillar integrates probabilistic risk assessment with scenario simulation, enabling administrators to evaluate the likelihood and impact of identified risks under varying institutional conditions. Automated prioritisation directs institutional attention toward the highest-consequence risks in real time, replacing reactive crisis management with proactive strategic governance. Risk interdependencies are also captured explicitly, as declining enrolment, financial constraints, and programme quality are causally linked.

4.4 Pillar 3: Fuzzy Logic-Based Uncertainty Representation

The third pillar addresses human ambiguity in institutional decisionmaking. Educational governance decisions are characterised by inputs that are inherently imprecise and judgements expressed in natural language. Fuzzy logic provides a mathematically rigorous framework for reasoning under these conditions. The fuzzy MCDM engine accepts linguistic inputs such as "very high risk" or "moderate compliance" from multiple stakeholders and encodes them as membership functions. An aggregation mechanism combines these potentially conflicting inputs into a coherent, prioritised assessment that is analytically defensible even under substantial uncertainty.

4.5 Pillar 4: Institutional Trust-Centric

The fourth pillar recognises that technical capability alone is insufficient for institutional impact. Every recommendation generated by the system must be accompanied by a traceable account of the decision logic in institutional terms, identifying which data inputs were most influential and which policy constraints shaped the recommendation. Accountability is ensured through auditable decision workflows that record which recommendations were generated and acted upon. Usability is validated through user-centred design methods including cognitive walkthrough analysis, think-aloud protocol studies, and structured usability testing involving academic administrators and quality assurance officers.

4.6 Framework Integration

The four pillars are mutually reinforcing. Predictive intelligence feeds risk indicators into the risk modelling layer. The FMCDM engine propagates uncertainty transparently into risk assessments and decision outputs. The usability pillar ensures that all analytical outputs are accessible and interpretable to institutional users. Table 3 shows the mapping between identified gaps and the corresponding pillars.

TABLE III. Mapping of Identified Gaps to AIDSS-HLE Pillars

Gap	Pillar	Mechanism	Expected Outcome
Task-Specific Isolation	All pillars	Unified governance architecture	Institution-wide intelligence
Logical Rigidity	Pillar 3	Fuzzy MCDM engine	Ambiguity-tolerant decisions
Data Mismatch	Pillar 1	ML and NLP components	Real-time, proactive insights

Trust Deficit	Pillar 4	XAI and usability validation	Trustworthy, adoptable system
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5. DISCUSSION

The integrated AI-driven DSS framework makes several contributions to the theoretical and practical understanding of decision support in higher education. Theoretically, the framework extends the classical DSS taxonomy by proposing an integrated governance-driven category that encompasses predictive, risk-aware, and uncertainty-sensitive capabilities as co-equal architectural requirements. It also contributes to the AI in education literature by positioning AI as a governance infrastructure rather than merely a personalised learning tool.

For higher education practitioners, the framework offers a practical roadmap for adopting AI-driven decision support grounded in both technical rigour and human-centred design. The automated policy tracking and real-time compliance monitoring capabilities are particularly relevant for Malaysian public universities operating under the oversight of the Malaysian Qualifications Agency (MQA) and the Ministry of Higher Education (KPT), where periodic programme review creates significant administrative burden.

As a conceptual framework, it has not yet been empirically validated. This is an acknowledged limitation, and the primary motivation for the research agenda proposed below.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes the integrated AI-driven DSS framework as a response to the limitations of conventional DSS in modern higher education. The framework is built on four interdependent pillars, including AI-Driven Predictive Intelligence, Risk-Aware Modelling, Fuzzy Logic-Based Uncertainty Representation, and Institutional Trust-Centric that together address the four critical gaps identified in the literature: task-specific isolation, logical rigidity, data architecture mismatch, and the trust and adoption deficit.

The proposed framework advances the discourse on intelligent academic governance and provides a foundation for future system development and empirical validation. In the future, expert validation studies involving academic administrators and quality assurance professionals will be conducted to assess the completeness and practical relevance of the framework. Prototype development focusing on the fuzzy MCDM engine and the predictive student risk module is also planned, followed by empirical evaluation in a real institutional context.

REFERENCES

1. Zhou, Y. (2026). The Impact of Declining Fertility Rates on Higher Education: Global Trends, Challenges, and Solutions. *Education Sciences*, 16(3), 372.
2. Neeraja, B., Jayanthi, B. V., Suchitra, S., Devendran, A., Kumar, K. A., & Ananth, C. (2026). Employees' Well-Being in Accreditation Environments: A Comparative Analysis of Higher Education Accreditation and Chemical Industry Certification Processes. *SAP Superintelligence Series*, 3, 47-47.
3. Gkrimpizi, T., Peristeras, V., & Magnisalis, I. (2023). Classification of barriers to digital transformation in higher education institutions: Systematic literature review. *Education sciences*, 13(7), 746.
4. Khan, N. A., Ahmad, M., Akhtar, M. M., Rajeyyagari, S., & Siddiqi, A. M. U. (2025). Transformative Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Higher Education: A Comprehensive Analysis of Pedagogical Innovation, Institutional Transformation, and Future Learning

- Ecosystems. Institutional Transformation, and Future Learning Ecosystems (November 19, 2025).
5. Gaftandzhieva, S., Hussain, S., Hilcenko, S., Doneva, R., & Boykova, K. (2023). Data-driven decision making in higher education institutions: State-of-play. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 14(6).
 6. Chnigri, Y., Sadik, M., & Slimani, H. (2024). Mapping The Literature On Intelligent Systems And Decision Support In Higher Education: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Management Control, Auditing And Finance Review (Mcafr)*, 1(2), 313-335.
 7. Djurayeva, G., Sagdullaeva, D., Shanazarova, G., Khidirova, M., Hamroyev, S., Dustmurodov, O., & Kodirova, R. N. (2025, December). Development of an AI-DSS Model To Support Financial and Managerial Decision-Making in Higher Education Institutions through The Integration Of Smart Campus Systems. In *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Future Networks and Distributed Systems* (pp. 299-306).
 8. Ahsan, M. A., Geman, O., Correia, S. D., & Zahid, M. (2025). A Smart Decision Support Framework: Leveraging AI and Business Intelligence for Sustainable Higher Education. *International Journal of Management and Data Intelligence*, 1(1).
 9. Zeng, Q., Zhang, H., & Li, C. (2026). Intelligent Hybrid Decision Support Systems for Education Policy and Institutional Performance Optimization. *Scientific Reports*.
 10. Sharma, S., Panda, S. P., & Verma, S. (2026). Modeling And Predicting Student Enrolment: A Meta-Learning Perspective. *International Journal of Information Technology*, 1-9.
 11. Kujur, A. G. P., Tiwari, R. K., & Panday, V. (2023, April). Student Performance Monitoring System Using Artificial Intelligence Models. In *International Conference on Recent Trends in Artificial Intelligence and IoT* (pp. 3-18). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
 12. Jakkaladiki, S. P., Janečková, M., Krunčík, J. A. N., Malý, F., & Otčenášková, T. (2023). Deep learning-based education decision support system for student E-learning performance prediction. *Scalable Computing: Practice and Experience*, 24(3), 327-338.
 13. Yan, J. (2025, September). Research on the Application of Artificial Intelligence in Educational Management Decision Support. In *Proceedings of the 2025 8th International Conference on Computer Information Science and Artificial Intelligence* (pp. 172-176).
 14. Fakeeh, K. A. (2015). Decision Support System (DSS) in Higher Education System. *International Journal of Applied Information System (IJAIS)*, 9(2).
 15. Mansmann, S., & Scholl, M. H. (2007). Decision support system for managing educational capacity utilization. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 50(2), 143-150.
 16. Muharlisiani, L. T., Mulawarman, W. G., Suwarni, S., Hutahaean, B., & Rahim, R. (2023). Designing a Decision Support System for Educational Resource Allocation. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 15(3), 4216-4225.
 17. Novianto, A. Y. (2023). Optimizing Scholarship Selection: A Decision Support System Approach Using the Analytical Hierarchy Process. *TIERS Information Technology Journal*, 4(2), 144-149.
 18. Alowaijl, A., Al-Shqeerat, K. H., & Hadwan, M. (2021). A multi-criteria assessment of decision support systems in educational environments. *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, 22(2), 985-996.
 19. Mora, M., Wang, F., Gómez, J. M., Rainsinghani, M. S., & Shevchenko, V. S. T. (2017). Decision-making support systems in quality management of higher education institutions: A

- selective review. *International Journal of Decision Support System Technology (IJDSST)*, 9(2), 56-79.
20. Savvadelli, E., Kiouvrekis, Y., & Kokkinaki, A. (2025, July). A Literature Review on Rule-Based Systems as Decision Support Systems. In *International Symposium on Human Aspects of Information Security and Assurance* (pp. 376-388). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
 21. Rodríguez, J. A. L., Díaz, N. D., & González, C. D. B. (2024). Optimizing education with data analytics: A feature comparison of LMS and SIS.
 22. Saeed, M. K., Shah, A. M., Mahmood, K., Ul Hassan, M., Khan, J. A. H. A. N. G. I. R., & Nawaz, B. A. B. A. R. (2021). Usage of internet of things (iot) technology in the higher education sector. *Journal of engineering science and technology*, 16(5), 4181-4191.
 23. Mallik, S., & Gangopadhyay, A. (2023). Proactive and reactive engagement of artificial intelligence methods for education: a review. *Frontiers in artificial intelligence*, 6, 1151391.
 24. Wang, S., Wang, F., Zhu, Z., Wang, J., Tran, T., & Du, Z. (2024). Artificial intelligence in education: A systematic literature review. *Expert systems with applications*, 252, 124167.
 25. Villar, A., & de Andrade, C. R. V. (2024). Supervised machine learning algorithms for predicting student dropout and academic success: a comparative study. *Discover Artificial Intelligence*, 4(1), 2.
 26. Kastrati, Z., Dalipi, F., Imran, A. S., Pireva Nuci, K., & Wani, M. A. (2021). Sentiment analysis of students' feedback with NLP and deep learning: A systematic mapping study. *Applied Sciences*, 11(9), 3986.
 27. Shaik, T., Tao, X., Dann, C., Xie, H., Li, Y., & Galligan, L. (2023). Sentiment analysis and opinion mining on educational data: A survey. *Natural Language Processing Journal*, 2, 100003.
 28. Kurnia, F., & Amri, M. K. (2026). Implementation Of Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (FAHP) and TOPSIS for Scholarship Decision Support System for the Underprivable. *Science, Technology, and Communication Journal*, 6(2), 95-104.
 29. Wei, C. C., Tai, C. C., Lee, S. C., & Chang, M. L. (2023). Assessing knowledge quality using fuzzy MCDM model. *Mathematics*, 11(17), 3673.
 30. Nazaretsky, T., Mejia-Domenzain, P., Swamy, V., Frej, J., & Käser, T. (2025). The critical role of trust in adopting AI-powered educational technology for learning: An instrument for measuring student perceptions. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 8, 100368.
 31. Nazaretsky, T., Ariely, M., Cukurova, M., & Alexandron, G. (2022). Teachers' trust in AI-powered educational technology and a professional development program to improve it. *British journal of educational technology*, 53(4), 914-931.